

Hospital readiness in implementing credentials, verification and readiness of medical personnel according to Staff Qualification and Education (SQE) assessment element 10 accreditation standards in Regional General Hospitals of West Muna District Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia, 2023

Sartini Risky MS^{1,*} and Rahman²

¹ *Nursing Sciences Study, Health Science Faculty, Mandala Waluya University, Kendari, Indonesia.*

² *Public Health Department, Public Health Faculty, Halu Oleo University, Kendari, Indonesia.*

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Abstract

Background: National data for 2022 records that 3,120 hospitals have been registered, of which 78.8% (2,482 units) of hospitals have been accredited and 638 hospitals (21.2%) have not been accredited. In Southeast Sulawesi there are 38 hospitals spread across all districts and cities, including 12.9 plenary accreditations, 5.3% main accreditations, 18.4% intermediate accreditations and 10.53 basic accreditations. Meanwhile, the regional general hospital in West Muna Regency is still basic accredited and continues to strive to improve the quality of service by preparing the implementation of medical personnel readiness, credentials and verification. The aim of this research is to see the readiness of hospitals in implementing credentials, verification and readiness of medical personnel based on the SQE assessment elements of 10 accreditation standards at the West Muna Regency Hospital.

Method: This research uses a qualitative method with a case study design, the informants in this research were 16 people from government agencies, professional organizations, civil service, medical committees and doctors at the West Muna Regency Regional Hospital. Next, interviews were conducted using interview

Result: The results of the research show that the West Muna Regency regional general hospital is ready to implement credentials which are marked by the recruitment of medical personnel, there are regulations in the recruitment of medical personnel, there is a credential flow and also medical personnel credential files. However, in its implementation, the West Muna Regency regional general hospital also experienced obstacles such as completeness of files and readiness of the bestari partners themselves. 2) Based on the research results, the West Muna Regency regional general hospital is also ready to verify medical personnel files. Validation of documents is carried out through the relevant site. 3) The West Muna Regency regional general hospital is also ready in terms of medical personnel to carry out qualifications and education for medical personnel. This can be seen from the regular monitoring and evaluation of STR or registration certificate and SIP or practice license for medical personnel and the existence of regulations governing STR or registration certificate for medical personnel.

Kesimpulan: West Muna District Hospital is ready to implement credentialing, verification and readiness of medical personnel according to the SQE 10 accreditation standard assessment elements. So hospitals need to increase their bestari partners through communication with professional organizations, equipping medical personnel resources according to service needs to the community and preparing infrastructure so that the health service process is more optimal.

Keywords: Readiness; Credentials; Verification; Medical Personnel; Hospital.

* Corresponding author: Sartini Risky

1. Introduction

Based on data collected by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia (2022) it is recorded that 3,120 hospitals have been registered, 78.8% (2,482 units) of hospitals have been accredited and 638 hospitals (21.2%) have not been accredited. By 2024, the government hopes that all hospitals in Indonesia will be accredited in accordance with the targets of the National Medium Term Development Plan (RPJMN) for 2020 – 2024 [1].

Based on data from the Southeast Sulawesi Health Service, there are 38 hospitals spread across all districts and cities. Bahteramas Hospital, Siloam Hospital, Hati Mulya Hospital, Hermina Kendari Hospital, Antam Pomalaa Hospital, Benyamin Guluh Kolaka Hospital and dr. L.M Baharuddin, M.Kes of which 2 has plenary accreditation (12.9%). Two hospitals are primarily accredited (5.3%), of the 38 hospitals, 7 of them are still intermediately accredited (18.4%) and there are still 10.53% of hospitals that are basic accredited and the rest are primary accredited. Meanwhile, the Regional General Hospital of West Muna Regency is still basic accredited [2]. One of the hospitals that will improve the quality of service according to accreditation standards is the West Muna District Hospital.

In order to achieve the hospital mission and to meet patient needs, hospitals need medical staff. The selection of medical staff is based on the recommendations of hospital leadership through a recruitment, appointment and evaluation process. The performance of medical staff will greatly influence patient safety in hospitals, for this reason hospitals need to implement clinical management [3].

Improving hospital quality is assessed by meeting predetermined development standards. These assessment standards are contained in hospital accreditation standards. One of the assessment elements in accreditation is Staff Qualifications and Education (SQE), which regulates the qualifications of medical personnel in hospitals. The SQE element is an important assessment in hospital accreditation where this standard determines the qualifications of Human Resources (HR) who will provide health services in hospitals. [4].

The SQE points state that hospitals require a variety of skills and staff qualifications to achieve the hospital's vision and mission and meet patient needs. Hospitals must ensure that the staff who work match the educational qualifications and needs of patients/clients. However, hospitals also need to carry out a credentialing process for medical personnel because they are involved in serving patients and hospitals need to provide opportunities to develop education, professionalism and personality for staff [5].

Staff qualifications and education as an element in hospital accreditation regulate several matters relating to human resources. Setiawan et.al (2021) stated in their research results that the role of medical personnel, nurses, medical recorders and other health service staff had a major impact on assessing service quality [6]

Recruitment of medical personnel based on SQE 10 means that every medical personnel who will start working in a hospital must go through a credentialing process carried out by medical personnel and already have a certificate or a bestari partner (doctor who has a certificate from another hospital). With credentials we can assess the level of competency of a medical worker by determining the limits of clinical authority he or she has in order to provide medical services to patients. Apart from that, SQE 10 also regulates the credentials of medical personnel who oversee the recruitment process to the placement of medical personnel, regulates validation and completeness. in the implementation of the credentials themselves, then recredentials and assignments for medical personnel [7].

West Muna District Hospital continues to strive to improve the quality of service, including in terms of implementing Staff Qualifications and Education (SQE) 10 for medical personnel, starting from credentials, medical personnel, verification and validation in the implementation of credentials, credentials to assignment of medical personnel. Nowadays, doctors in the Emergency Unit (ER) sometimes still under-diagnose, and when carrying out surgical procedures, sometimes the actions are still stiff and not yet smooth/agile, thus affecting the service to patients. Under-diagnostics means determining the diagnosis by emergency room doctors after carrying out anamnesis and physical examination which is still not optimal, meaning there are several diagnoses which do not match the results of 7 examinations by specialist doctors / Doctors in Charge of Services or DPJP so there is concern that this could affect the accuracy in decision making regarding treatment. towards these patients which in the end can affect the patient's recovery rate and the patient's length of stay. This underdiagnostic event at the West Muna Regional Hospital occurred in cases of internal medicine and surgery based on the results of discussions with the DPJP for internal medicine and surgery.

2. Method

This research uses a qualitative method with a case study design. The informants in this research were 16 people from government agencies, professional organizations, civil service, medical committees and doctors at the West Muna Regency Regional Hospital. Next, an interview was conducted using an interview guide.

3. Result and Discussion

Table 1 Credential Readiness According to the SQE 10 Assessment Element Assessment at West Muna District Hospital

Credential	
Recruitment of medical personnel	Credential barriers
Registration documents	Recruitment Regulations
Complete credential file	Credential flow

Based on the hierarchy diagram above, it can be concluded that West Muna District Hospital is ready to implement medical personnel credentials. This is characterized by several things, namely the credential component built by the recruitment of medical personnel, the medical personnel registration document which is the main part of the credential. Even though the credential has been implemented, obstacles are still found in its implementation, namely the lack of bestari partners in implementing the credential. However, if seen from the hierarchy diagram, the portion of this obstacle is not dominant, meaning it does not affect the implementation of credentials. Next, regulations for recruitment of medical personnel, completeness of medical personnel documents and credential flow, although they have a small portion, these 3 stages are the building blocks of the Credential component. As the results of the following interview::

"...the recruitment process for medical personnel at the West Muna Regency General Hospital involves submitting an application file addressed to the hospital director, which will be followed by the disposition of the medical personnel's application to the administrative sector, followed by the study of the application file by the credentials sub-committee. will also schedule assessment meetings for medical personnel or doctors who will work in the medical committee meeting room..." (Sd, 36 years)

Furthermore, the informant also stated that:

"...the medical personnel submit application files to the director of the West Muna Regional Hospital, then the director of the West Muna Regional Hospital makes a disposition regarding the medical personnel's application files through the Head of Administration or Head of Administrative Subdivision and the Chair of the Medical Committee related to the recruitment process, then the head of administrative division or Head of Subdivision The staff will of course study the application file and continue with an interview by the director or administrative management of the prospective medical personnel, then the medical committee, in this case the credentials sub-committee, will schedule a credential assessment meeting for the medical personnel in the medical committee meeting room..." (Jn, 39 years).

The informant also stated that:

"Sometimes the application files of the medical personnel concerned are incomplete and usually the bestari partners are ready" (Nrh, 34 years).

Furthermore, the informant stated that:

"There were several obstacles found in the field, namely firstly the medical personnel application files were incomplete because there were several documents that were left behind or not prepared, and then the readiness of the bestari partners to carry out the credentials" (Iba, 34 years)

The credential component of the information from the informants has been implemented, namely the recruitment of medical personnel in accordance with established regulations. In this recruitment, medical personnel must also include documents as a requirement for providing health services and after that the credentialing process will be carried out by the medical committee. However, this credentialing has not been implemented for all doctors due to several obstacles such as the completeness of the documents themselves and the readiness of bestari partners to assess doctors who will

be credentialed. This process is in line with the Hospital Accreditation Standards issued by the Ministry of Health which is a reference for all hospitals in Indonesia (1).

Credentials are a key element in reducing the risk of litigation (lawsuits in court) against hospitals and the doctors who work there. Monitoring and evaluating quality standards and doctor services in effective therapeutic transactions also needs to be carried out because it can reduce the risk of unexpected events (KTD) in patients by minimizing therapeutic errors provided by general practitioners and specialist doctors who hold certain clinical authority in the hospital (8).

Table 2 Kesiapan Tenaga Medis Dalam Penerapan Kualifikasi Dan Pendidikan Menurut Elemen Penilaian SQE 10 di RSUD Kabupaten Muna Barat

Kredensial	
	Regulasi STR
Monev STR dan SIP	
	SIP

In the medical personnel component, it can be seen that STR evaluation monitoring has been carried out, and this evaluation monitoring has a larger proportion, apart from medical personnel, which in this case are general practitioners and specialist doctors, the West Muna District Hospital also has them. Then, based on the hierarchy diagram, it can be seen that checking the STR of medical personnel is carried out through the STR validation site and there are also regulations governing STR, SIP and the validity period of STR. Based on this, it can be concluded that the variable medical personnel are ready at the West Muna District Hospital. As the results of the following interview:

... "To monitor the validity period of the STR of all medical personnel at the West Muna Hospital, a kind of control table was created in the staffing, the control table is filled with data about the STR of all medical personnel and that includes the validity period and it is verified by the staff every six months, so in this way it is hoped that the validity period of the STR of medical personnel and other health personnel can be well controlled so that before the validity period of the STR ends..." (Llk, 48 years).

Furthermore, the informant also stated that:

"The validity period of the STR and its monitoring, the West Muna Regional Hospital monitors and evaluates the validity period of medical personnel by collecting all data on medical personnel and making a control table for the validity period of STR and SIP" (Ts, 56 years).

Medical personnel are the second component in implementing the qualifications and education of medical personnel. From the results of the data collected, it can be seen that monitoring and determining the qualifications of medical personnel who will work or have already worked at the West Muna Regency Regional Hospital is given great attention. This is proven by the credentialing process that has been implemented and also for the STR of medical personnel, monitoring and evaluation is always carried out to determine the active period. from the STR and SIP of medical personnel so that the hospital can provide a warning to the doctor concerned to arrange for an STR extension. A medical worker is required to take part in various competency improvement activities to improve the quality of service to patients, as well as to get grades as a basis for getting an STR extension. If you have received an STR, it will be the basis for processing the SIP.

The West Muna Regency Hospital also has various qualifications and education for medical personnel, where there are 6 general practitioners and 7 specialist doctors consisting of obstetrics and gynecology specialists, pediatricians, radiology specialists, anesthesiologists and dentists. Even though specialist doctors are not yet complete in all areas of knowledge, the composition of doctors they have is capable of providing health services. Because as is known, the lack of medical personnel is influenced by several factors, such as limited budgets for providing medical personnel and doctors with the knowledge desired by the West Muna Regency Regional Hospital are not available.

Hospitals must offer staff members opportunities to advance their education, grow as people and build their professionalism. Therefore, it is important to provide staff with opportunities for in-service education and other types of learning [9].

The ethical responsibility of a medical worker is not only about attitude and knowledge, but also about how medical staff should act [10]. In carrying out their profession, doctors have special authority (privilege) because they study the human body. This authority is based on professional ethical responsibilities which are determined by legal norms originating from law and legislation. Professional ethics as rules that act on community groups that regulate reciprocal relationships between both parties, namely between group members or community members who serve and those who are served [11]

Table 3 Readiness for File Verification According to SQE 10 Assessment Elements at West Muna District Hospital

Medical Personnel Verification		
	STR validation site	Diploma validation
Diploma validation	STR & SIP validation	

The picture above shows that the West Muna District Hospital has carried out verification of medical personnel eligibility files

Based on the results of the interview, monitoring and evaluation of the STR and SIP of medical personnel is always carried out periodically and for medical personnel whose SIP validity period is about to end, the hospital will notify the medical personnel. Apart from that, validation has also been carried out for medical personnel's documents, including diplomas, STRs and SIPs. As the results of the following interview:

"...for the verification process of the files submitted from the start by the medical personnel, we state that they are complete and valid and have been verified before entering the credentials, so this verification is mandatory" (Yrk, 32 years).

Furthermore, the informant also stated that:

"...the one who did it was the civil service sub-section of the West Muna District Hospital" (Yrk, 32 years old)

The informant also stated that:

"...so for this validity process or diploma examination, check on the kemendikbud.go.id site so we can enter the site then we enter the full name of the medical personnel then from there all the campus names, diplomas, study programs will appear, so everything is done. complete from there" (Yrk, 32 years).

Furthermore, the informant also stated that:

"Yes, it is absolutely correct that the file verification process is still being carried out, where the medical personnel file verification process is carried out by the West Muna Hospital by the personnel department of the West Muna Regional Hospital itself" (Sfr, 28 years).

The informant also stated that:

"...to check the validity, the validity test of the medical professional education certificate is carried out by checking on the website kemendikbud.go.id..." (Sfr, 28 years old)

Verification of medical personnel files is always carried out routinely and periodically where the hospital records the validity period of the medical personnel's practice documents. Apart from that, the STR of medical personnel will be verified and revalidated by the hospital via the official website of the Indonesian Medical College. Of course, this process refers to the rules or regulations regarding STR that have been set at the West Muna District Hospital. Verification and validation are not only carried out on medical personnel's STRs but also on medical personnel's diplomas, transcripts and SIPs.

Verification and validation of medical personnel files is carried out to ensure that doctors who register at the West Muna Regency Regional Hospital are truly doctors who are supported by medical personnel documents. Verification and validation of files is also to find out the validity period of the STR and SIP where the hospital will check the validity period of the STR and SIP so that doctors can be reminded to take care of extending the STR and SIP, namely 6 months

before the validity period expires. If medical personnel do not renew, the hospital will revoke the doctor's clinical authority and be prohibited from providing health services and may only provide administrative services until the STR and SIP have been extended.

4. conclusion

The West Muna Regency Regional Hospital is ready to implement credentials which are marked by the recruitment of medical personnel, there are regulations for the recruitment of medical personnel, there is a credential flow and also the credential files for medical personnel are complete. However, in its implementation, West Muna District Hospital also experienced obstacles such as completeness of files and readiness of the bestari partners themselves. In terms of medical personnel, the implementation of qualifications and education of medical personnel. This can be seen from the regular monitoring and evaluation of STR and SIP for medical personnel and the existence of regulations governing STR for medical personnel. In terms of verifying medical personnel files. Validation of documents is carried out through the relevant site.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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